

First Planck time
Snapshot

(Picture
a)

Second Snapshot

(Picture
b)

Quantum Information Holography (QIH) Velocity, Acceleration and Probability Encoding

In the framework of QIH, the universe is perceived as a quantum computational process where every bit of information is encoded in quantum state vectors (QSUs) on Planck scale qubits. These qubits are fundamental building block of information. These QSUs not only define the instantaneous properties of particles and fields but also their evolution over time.

Spacetime in QIH is composed of a lattice of Planck-scale qubits, which is an enhanced version of Einstein's vector tensor field. In QIH, this tensor field is enhanced into a quantum state vector tensor field that incorporates dynamics, gravity, and probability.

Encoding Instantaneous Velocity and Probability

At any given Planck time snapshot, a quantum state vector (QSV) on a qubit can be represented by an angle θ .

This angle encodes both the instantaneous velocity components and the probabilities of the qubit being in a state 0 or 1.

Instantaneous Velocity Components

The velocity components in the x and y directions are given by:

$$V_x = c \cos(\theta), \quad V_y = c \sin(\theta)$$

where c is the speed of light

θ is the orientation of the QSV relative to the qubit axis.

In picture "a" the QSU is at a 60-degree angle. The velocity components encoded into the QSU relative to the qubit axis:

$$V_x = c \cos(60^\circ) = 0.5c$$

$$V_y = c \sin(60^\circ) = 0.866c$$

Instantaneous Probability Encoded by angle θ of QSU

The probability of the qubit being in a state of 0 or 1 are given by:

$$P(0) = \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \quad P(1) = \sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$$

where θ is the orientation of the QSU relative to the qubit axis.

In picture "a" the QSV orientation, θ , is 60° . This encodes the probability the qubit will be a 0 or 1.

For a 60° QSV:

$$\text{Probability qubit is 0} = \cos^2\left(\frac{60}{2}\right) = 0.75 = 75\%$$

$$\text{Probability qubit is 1} = \sin^2\left(\frac{60}{2}\right) = 0.25 = 25\%$$

One Planck Time Later

One Planck time later, a new QSV is emitted onto the qubit, potentially with a different angle. In picture "b" the new QSV is at a 15° degree angle:

New Instantaneous Velocity Components

$$V_x = c \cos(15^\circ) = 0.966c$$

$$V_y = c \sin(15^\circ) = 0.259c$$

New Instantaneous Probability

Probability qubit is 0, $P(0) = \cos^2\left(\frac{15^\circ}{2}\right) = 0.933$

Probability qubit is 1, $P(1) = \sin^2\left(\frac{15^\circ}{2}\right) = 0.067$

$P(0) = 93.3\%$ and $P(1) = 6.7\%$

Rate of Change and Acceleration

The change, geometrically and informationally, over one Planck time gives the acceleration, which is equivalent to gravity in this context.

Acceleration Components

Using the velocities from the previous and current Planck time snapshot ("a" and "b"), the acceleration in the X and Y directions are:

$$a_x = \frac{v_{x,new} - v_{x,old}}{t_p} = \frac{0.966c - 0.5c}{5.39 \times 10^{-44}}$$

$$a_x \approx \frac{0.466c}{5.39 \times 10^{-44}} \approx 2.59 \times 10^{51} \text{ m/s}^2$$

$$a_y = \frac{v_{y,new} - v_{y,old}}{t_p} = \frac{0.259c - 0.866c}{5.39 \times 10^{-44}}$$

$$a_y \approx \frac{-0.607c}{5.39 \times 10^{-44}} \approx -3.38 \times 10^{51} \text{ m/s}^2$$

(b)

Rate of Change of Probability

The rate of change of the probabilities of the qubit being in state 0 or 1 is given by:

Chain Rule

$$\frac{dP(0)}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\cos^2 \left(\frac{\theta}{2} \right) \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \sin(\theta) \cdot \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

$$\frac{dP(1)}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\sin^2 \left(\frac{\theta}{2} \right) \right) = \frac{1}{2} \sin(\theta) \cdot \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

Encoding Gravity and Probability into the Informational Substrate of Space time.

In QIH, the instantaneous velocity components and probabilities are encoded in the quantum state vectors of the qubits that make up the fabric of spacetime. When these QSVs change, they provide information about both the acceleration

about both the acceleration (equivalent to gravity) and the evolution of quantum states (probabilities). This directly ties the geometrical and informational aspects of spacetime.

Mathematical Equivalence to GR and QM

General Relativity (GR) Tensor Equation

Einstein's field equations in GR are:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$$

In QIH, the enhanced quantum state vector tensor field $\Psi_{\mu\nu}$ incorporates dynamics and probability:

$$\Psi_{\mu\nu} = \sum_i c_i \psi_i e^{i\theta_i}$$

Ψ is the enhanced tensor field in QIH that encapsulates the quantum state vectors (QSVs). It is analogous to the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ in GR, but it includes additional information about quantum states and their dynamics.

Role of Ψ : It represents the complete state of the quantum system, including its geometry, dynamics, and probabilistic nature.

$\sum_i$ - Summation Over Quantum States

• Description: This summation indicates that the tensor field $\Psi_{\mu\nu}$ is constructed from contributions of multiple quantum states (QSVs).

• Role: It ensures that all relevant quantum states are included in the tensor field, providing a comprehensive description of the system.

C_i - Coefficients

- Description: C_i are coefficients that weight each quantum state vector ψ_i in the summation.
- Role: They represent the probability amplitudes or the contribution strength of each quantum state to the overall tensor field. These coefficients are crucial for defining the superposition of states.

ψ_i - Quantum State Vectors

- Description: ψ_i are the individual quantum state vectors that form the basis of the tensor field.
- Role: Each ψ_i represents a specific quantum state of the system. These vectors are fundamental components that encode the physical properties and dynamics of the system.

$e^{i\theta i}$ - Phase Factor

• Description: $e^{i\theta i}$ is the complex exponential function representing the phase factor of each quantum state.

• Role: The phase factor $e^{i\theta i}$ incorporates the dynamical evolution and the interference effects of the quantum states. The angle θ , can change over time, encoding information about the state's phase evolution.

Summary of Components

- $\Psi_{\mu\nu}$: The enhanced quantum state vector tensor field that encapsulates the quantum information of the system.

- $\sum_j$: Summation over all contributing quantum states.

- C_j : Coefficients representing the probability amplitude of each quantum state.

- ψ_j : Quantum state vectors representing the individual quantum states.

- $e^{i\theta_j}$: Phase factors encoding the dynamical evolution of each quantum state.

Role of $\Psi_{\mu\nu}$ in QIH

The enhanced tensor field $\Psi_{\mu\nu}$ in QIH provides a unified framework that incorporates the geometry, dynamics, and probabilistic aspects of spacetime. It enhances Einstein's metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ by including quantum mechanical properties, thereby bridging the gap between GR and QM. This unified field encapsulates how the quantum state vectors evolve over time, how they interfere, and how they contribute to the curvature and dynamics of spacetime.

Equivalence with GR and QM

• GR: The Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ in GR describes how matter and energy curve spacetime. In QIH, $\Psi_{\mu\nu}$ captures the same curvature effects through the sum of QSL_k , providing an equivalent description of spacetime dynamics.

• QM: The probability amplitudes and phase factors in QIH align with the principles of QM, where the wave function Ψ describes the probabilistic descriptions in QM, showing their equivalence.

Equating Ψ to the classical Einstein Tensor:

$$\text{We equate } \Psi = \sum_i c_i \psi_i e^{i\theta_i}$$

to the classical Einstein tensor:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$$

where $\Psi_{\mu\nu}$ represents the quantum-enhanced curvature of spacetime. The stress-energy tensor in QIH is:

$$T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{QIH}} = \frac{\hbar}{c} \sum_i |\psi_i|^2$$

Thus

$$\sum_i c_i \psi_i e^{i\theta_i} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_i c_i \psi_i e^{i\theta_i} \right)_{g_{\mu\nu}} + \Delta g_{\mu\nu} =$$
$$= \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \left(\frac{\hbar}{c} \sum_i |\psi_i|^2 \right)$$

QM Wave Function

The Schrodinger equation in QM is

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \hat{H} \psi$$

In QM, the probabilities are given by:

$$P(0) = \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), P(1) = \sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$$

Their rate of change of these probabilities with respect to time can be calculated using the chain rule:

$$\frac{dP(0)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{2} \sin(\theta) \cdot \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

$$\frac{dP(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

These are analogous to the time dependant probability amplitudes in QM.

Conclusion

QIH shows that the universe operates as a five dimensional quantum holographic information system. Three spactial dimensions (x, y, z), one dimension of information and one dimension of time. Each Planck time snapshot encodes vital information about the state of the universe. The rate of change of these quantum state vectors provides a natural description of acceleration and probability (using only the speed of light as a QSU and its rate of change), seamlessly integrating QM with the curvature of spacetime.

This view implies that the geometry of QSVs is fundamentally indistinguishable from the geometry of curvature and probability, revealing the unity of information and physical reality.